

ARTICLE INFO

©2025 RS Publication

Paper ID: IJASTR-
6961D52858084

Published: 2026-01-12

DOI:

<https://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18221370>

Page No: 52-75

**ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL STUDIES OF THIOSEMICARBAZONE
COMPLEXES OF Vo(IV), Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II)**

Satendra Kumar

(Associate professor)

Department of Chemistry, Government Degree College, Hempur, Bisalpur
(Pilibhit)

✉ E-mail: drsatendrakmr@gmail.com

Mobile no.-9639505801

ABSTRACT:

Diamagnetic character and spectral bands around 19800 and 19420 cm^{-1} in the Ni(II) complexes indicate square planar geometry. The magnetic moments of the Ni(II) complexes are found in the range (1.75–1.82 B.M.) which are subnormal to the range (2.9–3.4 B.M.) normally expected for octahedral nickel complexes. In the electronic spectra of nickel complexes bands observed at 8510, 8475, 8530, 8583 (ν_1); 16100, 15870, 15860, 16130 (ν_2) and 25320, 25640, 24500, 24390 cm^{-1} (ν_3) are attributable to ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}$; ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ transitions respectively. The spectral data are utilized to compute important ligand field parameters using ligand field theory of spin allowed transition in d^8 configuration. The values of $10Dq$ and B can be utilized to

Cite This Paper: Dr Satendra Kumar (2026). "ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL STUDIES OF THIOSEMICARBAZONE COMPLEXES OF Vo(IV), Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II)". *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF ADVANCED SCIENTIFIC AND TECHNICAL RESEARCH (IJASTR)*, vol. 16, no. 1, 2026, pp. 52-75. DOI: <https://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18221370>

calculate ν_2^- and ν_3 . The electronic spectral data together with reported magnetic moment values suggest an octahedral geometry for the nickel complexes.

Copper(II) complex shows magnetic moment around 1.82 B.M. which is close to the spin only value for a d^9 ion. The electronic spectrum displays a broad band in vicinity of 17980 cm^{-1} which may be assigned to ${}^2E_g \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}$ transition indicating the presence of copper(II) ion in an octahedral field. The magnetic moment of the complex indicates no copper–copper interaction. The absence of any band below 10000 cm^{-1} or above 17000 cm^{-1} ruled out the possibility of tetrahedral or square planar symmetry. Broadness of the band in complexes may be due to Jahn Teller distortion.

Key Words: Ni (II) complexes, electronic spectrum, ligand field, charge–transfer band

INTRODUCTION:

Ligand field spectra or commonly known as electronic spectra^(1,2) is a important tool for determining valency, coordination of transition metal ions, establishing bonding between the ligand and the metal ions, particularly when different ligands are compared with respect to the same metal ion.

Transition metal complex can be characterized by two sets of parameters^(3–6) (a) The orbital energy difference in the partially filled shell. (b) The inter– electronic repulsions.

The spectra of the transition metal complexes can be interpreted with the aid of the ligand field theory. Application of this theory leads upto identification of the environment of the metal ions (its first coordination sphere by means its ligand field spectrum).

The electronic spectra of the complexes were recorded in acetone/dichloromethane with a Hitachi Perkin–Elmer model 20–200m μ spectro– photometer.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Selbin^(7,8) in his review articles has summarized electronic spectral data of a number of VO²⁺ complexes. In complexes three low intensity absorption bands are observed in the spectral region 8300–28600 cm⁻¹. These are usually known as (d–d) or ligand field bands, but for convenience selbin refer to these as band–I (between 11000–16000 cm⁻¹) band–II (between 14500–19000 cm⁻¹) and band–III (between 21000–30000 cm⁻¹). In these cases, (a) the third band III is not always observed, being often buried beneath a high intensity charge–transfer band (b) the wide range of energies for the three bands reflects the sensitivity of the electronic transitions to the environment of the VO²⁺ species. (c) VO(tart)²⁻ and VO(Lact)²⁻ ions gave four bands in this spectral region and (d) it is not yet possible to make meaningful assignments of the high intensity charge transfer type bands which have (occasionally) been reported in the UV region.

Furlani⁽⁹⁾, Feltham⁽¹⁰⁾, Jorgensen⁽¹¹⁾ and Ballhausen and Gray⁽¹²⁾ have proposed the crystal field models of the VO²⁺ ion. Ballhausen and Gray⁽¹²⁾ treated the molecule ion VO(H₂O)₅ and gave a energy level diagram. The molecular structure of ion VO(H₂O)₅ was assumed the same as that of VOSO₄.5H₂O except that the ligand trans to the oxide oxygen is a water molecule instead of a sulphate group. Such a change will have little effect on the energy states of the interest. The bonding scheme for VO(H₂O)₅²⁺ belonging to the C_{2v}–symmetry⁽¹²⁾ is a follows:

- (i) A strong σ –bond of a₁–symmetry between the (4s+3dz²) hybrid orbital of vanadium and (2s+2pz) hybrid orbital of oxygen. Two π –bonds of symmetry

between $3d_{xz}$ and $3d_{yz}$ orbitals of vanadium and $2p_x$ and $2p_y$ orbitals of oxygen.

Thus making a total of three vanadium oxygen bond thus imparting triple bond character of VO^{2+} entity.

- (ii) Four bonds involving $(2s+2p_z)$ hybrid orbitals of four equivalent water oxygen with $(4s-3d_{z^2})$ (bond of sym a_1), $4p_x$ and $4p_y$ (bond of sym e) and $3d_{x^2-y^2}$ (bond of sym b_1) orbitals of vanadium.
- (iii) The axial water oxygen is bonded to the up_z orbital of vanadium forming a σ -bond of a_1 symm.
- (iv) The $3d_{xy}$ vanadium orbital of sym b_2 remains non bonding.

The results of the calculation have shown that the order of the molecular orbitals is the same as shown in energy scheme. The transition of the nonbonding b_2 -electron to the $e\pi^*$, b_1^* and $1a_1^*$ molecular orbitals that are essentially the $3d$ -metal orbitals from the three ($d-d$) transitions.

From energy scheme Fig. (5.1) transitions to $2E(g)$, $2B_1$ and $2A_1$ will occur at increasingly higher energies. The electronic dipole vectors transfer as E and A, in C_{4v} symmetry. Hence the transitions to E and A, excited states are orbitally allowed and they can be expected to have some what greater intensity than the other crystal field transitions. From this observation, the first more intense band near 13000 cm^{-1} (ϵ , 20–25) is reasonably assigned to $2B_2 \rightarrow 2E_1$. The second transition occurring near 16000 cm^{-1} (ϵ , 5–15) appears as a weak shoulder and is assigned to $2B_2 \rightarrow 2B_1$ and it is allowed vibronically. The third transition $2B_2 \rightarrow 2A_1$ is observed only in a few vanadyl complexes like $VO(C_2O_4)_2^{2-}$, $(VO)_2(C_2O_4)_3^{2-}$, $VO(\text{enta})$, $VO(\text{acac})_2$ etc. near 30000 cm^{-1} ($\epsilon \sim 100$). Often the third band, usually a shoulder is not observed at all and it is presumed to be masked by the intense charge transfer bands.

The two charge transfer bands near 50000 cm^{-1} and below are due to the promotion of an electron from the oxygen π -orbital ($\epsilon\pi b$) to b_2 and $\epsilon\pi^*$ levels (Fig. 5.1). The first charge transfer band near 41700 cm^{-1} in $\text{VOSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ is assigned as due to the transition $2B_2 \rightarrow 2E(\pi)$. Calculations have shown that the second band found near 50000 cm^{-1} can be attributed to the second charge transfer band due to ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2B_2$ transition. The same type of charge transfer are expected to occur in all the vanadyl compounds.

It is to be noted that complexes like $\text{VO}(\text{acac})_2$ having a lower symmetry C_{2v} should give four bands due to (d-d) transitions. But $\text{VO}(\text{acac})_2$ shows only three bands at 12330 , 17820 and 26200 cm^{-1} (in water) and it may be presumed that the splitting of the $\epsilon\pi^*$ level caused by the lower symmetry is too small to be observed.

Since the transitions in $\text{VOSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ both in solution and in the solid state occur nearly in the same region, it is a convincing evidence that the solution should also contain VO^{2+} entity. Protonation of VO^{2+} , resulting in the formation of $\text{v}(\text{OH})_2$ would have significantly affected the amount of π -bonding and would largely affect the position of energy levels and hence the band maxima. Electronic spectral studies of some vanadyl complexes have also been studied at low temperature.⁽¹⁴⁾ At low temperature the broad band near 13000 cm^{-1} get split into three bands and considering the 17000 cm^{-1} band to be the last (d-d) band, four (d-d) bands are observed both for C_{2v} and C_{4v} vanadyl species.⁽¹⁵⁾ The band near 25000 cm^{-1} , which is the third (d-d) transition band by Ballhausen and Gray model is considered by ortolano⁽¹⁵⁾ et al to be the first charge transfer band. The appearance of four bands at low temperature for the C_{4v} -symmetry is explained by ortolano et al (Loc.Cit) in terms of the removal of degeneracy by spin-orbit

coupling. Thus ortolano et.al⁽¹⁶⁾ (Loc.Cit) made improvement in the Ballhausen and Gray scheme. Gray and Hare⁽¹⁷⁾ also proposed the same model to CrO^{3+} and MoO^{3+} .

Solvent effects of $\text{VO}(\text{acac})_2$ studies by Bernal and Riger⁽¹⁸⁾ are in good agreement with the MO predictions of Ballhausen and Gray. The optical data have been used by them to calculate 'g' values which are in good agreement with the e.s.r. results.

Here we report the VO^{2+} complexes of $(\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{21}\text{N}_7\text{S})$; $(\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{33}\text{N}_7\text{S})$ and $(\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{21}\text{N}_7\text{S})$ having penta coordinated environment. Assignment of bands made on the basis of earlier observations and the data included in table (5.1–5.3). Three low intensity absorption bands are observed at room temperature in the spectral region $8300\text{--}28600\text{ cm}^{-1}$, which by following^(19–21) Band I– $11000\text{--}16000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ Ballhausen and Band II– $14500\text{--}19000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ Gray (B.G.) scheme Band–III– $21000\text{--}30000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ have assigned to band–I (to the electron transition $b_2 \rightarrow e\pi^*$ (or ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2E_1$); band–II (to $b_2 \rightarrow b_1^*$ (or ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2B_1$) and band–III (to $b_2 \rightarrow 1a_1^*$ (or ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2A_1$). All other higher energy bands are assumed to be charge transfer in origin. According to vonquickenborne and McGlynn⁽²²⁾ the first band which is centered near 13000 cm^{-1} has been assigned to an unresolved band resulting from $dxy \rightarrow dyz$, dxz (${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2E_1$) transition. The second shoulder observed in the $15000\text{--}17500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region is attributed to $dxy \rightarrow dx^2 - y^2$ (${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2B_1$) and third band may either be assigned to the transition $dxy \rightarrow dz^2$ (${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2A_1$) or believed to arise from low energy charge transfer. The geometry of these neutral five coordinated mononuclear complexes, can be described in terms of a trigonal bipyramidal, distorted towards a tetragonal pyramidal or square pyramidal.^(23–25)

Cobalt(II) Complexes: Co(II) with d^7 configuration mostly form square planar/tetrahedral/pentagonal and octahedral complexes. In tetrahedral symmetry of

Co(II) complexes the 4F-ground state get split into 4A_2 , 4T_2 and ${}^4T_1(F)$ involving ${}^4A_2 \rightarrow {}^4T_2(\nu_1)$; ${}^4A_2 \rightarrow {}^4T_1(F)(\nu_2)$; and ${}^4A_2 \rightarrow {}^4T_1(P)(\nu_3)$ transitions which usually found in the region 3000–5000, 4500–9000 and 13000–17000 cm^{-1} .

In general, the ligand field spectra of octahedral Co(II) ions consist of two strong bands and one or two bands of weaker intensity. The first band ν_1 assigned to the transition ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$, is usually found in the 5000–10000 cm^{-1} region, the second band, ν_2 is a weak one but spin allowed, assigned to the transition ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}$ and found in the 12000–17000 cm^{-1} region the third band ν_3 , which is often split into two or three components is assigned to the transition ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$, 2G, 2P are usually found in the 16000–20000 cm^{-1} region.⁽²⁶⁾

In general the ligand field spectra of octahedral Co(II) ions consist of two strong bands and one or two bands of weaker intensity. The first band ν_1 – assigned to the transition ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$ is usually found in the 5500–10000 cm^{-1} region the second band ν_2 , is a weak one but spin allowed assigned to the transition ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}$ and found in the 12000–17000 cm^{-1} region the third band ν_3 which is often split into two or three components, is assigned to the transition ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$, 2G, 2P are usually found in the 16000–20000 cm^{-1} region.

The electronic spectra of all the complexes recorded herein are very similar with each other and consist of three bands at 8470, 8330, 18180, 17850 and 27850 and 26660 cm^{-1} attributable to ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(\nu_1)$; ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)(\nu_2)$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)(\nu_3)$ transitions respectively in favour of an octahedral field. In tables (5.4–5.6), the band maxima and their assignments and the calculated ligand field parameters are listed.

When all the bands ν_1 , ν_2 , ν_3 are observed to be free from shoulder, the ligand field parameters, Dq and B are in principle, calculated using first order perturbation theory⁽²⁷⁾ and the transition energies are given by the following equations.⁽²⁸⁾

$$\nu_1 = 5Dq - 7.5B + \frac{1}{2} (225B^2 + 100Dq^2 + 180 DqB) \frac{1}{2} \quad (i)$$

$$\nu_2 = 15Dq - 7.5B + \frac{1}{2} (225B^2 + 100Dq^2 + 180DqB) \frac{1}{2} \quad (ii)$$

$$\nu_3 = (225B + 100Dq + 180 DqB) \frac{1}{2} \quad (iii)$$

The methods of calculations of ligand field parameters from the ligand field spectra of octahedral Co(II) complexes have been discussed by Reedijk (Loc.Cit). The energy of ν_1 corresponds to $10Dq$ for weak field and the value of Dq is obtained from it. With these assignments B and Dq have also been calculated (Table 5.4–5.6).

Nickel(II) Complexes: Six coordinate nickel(II) complexes exhibit a spectrum involving three spin allowed transitions to ${}^3T_{2g}(F)(\nu_1)$; ${}^3T_{1g}(F)(\nu_2)$ and ${}^3T_{1g}(P)(\nu_3)$ from the ground state ${}^3A_{2g}(F)$. These occur in $7000\text{--}11000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (ν_1); $15000\text{--}19000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (ν_2) and $25000\text{--}29000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (ν_3) regions respectively. In addition to these two spin forbidden transitions to 1E_g and to ${}^1T_{2g}$ are frequently observed. A large number of complexes of the type $Ni(L_2)X_2$ are known^(29–42). Almost all the complexes of the type (Pseudo octahedral) show visible spectrum typical of regular octahedral complexes. The ν_2 and ν_3 bands are not greatly affected due to lowering of symmetry from O_h to D_{4h} , whereas ν_1 band is frequently split in two components, these are assigned to D_{4h} symmetry as transitions to the ${}^3B_{2g}$ and 3E_g (components of $T_{2g}(\nu_1)$ in O_h) levels and have energies of $10Dq(xy)$ and $10Dq(xy) - 35/4 Dt$, respectively. In certain cases the ν_3 band also shown signs of structure which has been attributed to the lower symmetry but which might also

represent a close lying triplet–singlet transition to the ${}^1T_{2g}$ level. The absorption spectra of some of the complexes of Ni(II) studied herein display four bands ca– 8000, 11000, 17500 and 27500 cm^{-1} where as rest of the complexes show only three bands. It may be assumed that the former type of complexes are psuedo– octahedral while the latter type may be regular octahedral. The bands at ca 17000 (ν_2) and 27000 cm^{-1} (ν_3) are characteristic of an octahedral complex where as the first band (ν_1) in latter type of the complexes appear at ca 11000 cm^{-1} and is split into two at ca 8000 and 11000 cm^{-1} in the former type complexes. The ν_1 – band in regular octahedral complexes directly yields the 10Dq value and in pseudo octahedral complexes, it is possible to calculate 10 Dq and B from the visible band energies but the results so obtained refer to the excited states and not to the ground state of the molecular, since the cauculated values do not agree well with the observed transitions. Conversely, if the position of ν_3 band is calculated from ν_1 and ν_2 then also the agreement with the ν_3 is very poor.

The band at ca. 11000 cm^{-1} in pseudo–octahedral complexes may well be tough to have arisen from ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^1T_2(D)$ transition^(36,39). The intensity of this band is comparable with the intensity of the first band suggesting its origin as due to the departure from Oh symmetry towards D4h. Assuming the D4h symmetry with the ligands coordinated along the Z–axis the most probable assignment would be ca. 8000 cm^{-1} (${}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3E_g$) and ca. 11000 cm^{-1} (${}^3B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3B_{2g}$) in these pseudo– octahedral complexes.

The ligand field parameters 10 Dq and B in octahedral complexes have been computed from equations suggested by Lever⁽⁴³⁾. These data are in good agreement with those reported for other octahedral complexes.

In the pseudo–octahedral complexes assuming weak ligand field, the in– plane ligand field strength $Dq(x)$ is obtained as $0.1 ({}^3B_{2g})$ while the axial ligand field strength $Dq(z)$ is $0.1 (2v^a {}^3E_g \rightarrow {}^3B_{2g})$. The tetragonality parameters D_s and D_t are given as:

$$D_t = 4/35 (v^3 B_{2g} \rightarrow v a {}^3 E_g) \text{ and}$$

$$D_s = 1/6 (v_b {}^3 E_g \rightarrow v_b {}^3 A_{2g} + 5/4 D_t), \text{ respectively.}$$

The ligand field parameters thus calculated are collected in Tables 5.7–5.8. The in–plane ligand field strength of present ligands are practically unchanged in the complexes $10Dq$ –ranging between 9000 and 10990 cm^{-1} , instead the axial ligand field strength is given $Dq(z)$, is distinctly lower than would be expected considering the known δ – and π –antibonding ability of the involved ligands, or of the known spectro chemical behaviour of the corresponding purely octahedral chromophores. In the corresponding NiCl_6 , NiBr_6 or $\text{Ni}(\text{NCS})_6$ the $10 Dq$ is of the order of 7200, 7000 and 9700 cm^{-1} respectively.

Comparing this with our results, we can say that there is weakening effect of axial ligand strength in the complexes. This weakening effect of the axial ligands is expected because the equatorial ligands exert a strong steric hindrance preventing axial ligands from approaching the central metal as closely as would be required for optimum covalent bonding.⁽⁴³⁾

Diamagnetic character and spectral bands around 19800 and 19420 cm^{-1} in the Ni(II) complexes indicate square planar geometry. The magnetic moments of the Ni(II) complexes are found in the range (1.75–1.82 B.M.) which are subnormal to the range (2.9–3.4 B.M.) normally expected for octahedral nickel complexes. In the electronic spectra of nickel complexes bands observed at 8510, 8475, 8530, 8583 (ν_1); 16100, 15870, 15860, 16130 (ν_2) and 25320, 25640, 24500, 24390 cm^{-1} (ν_3) are attributable to

${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}$; ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ transitions respectively. The spectral data are utilized to compute important ligand field parameters using ligand field theory of spin allowed transition in d^8 configuration^(44,45). The values of $10Dq$ and B can be utilized to calculate ν_2 and ν_3 . The electronic spectral data together with reported magnetic moment values suggest an octahedral geometry for the nickel complexes.^(46,47)

Copper Complexes: The electronic spectra of the complexes under four coordinated environment exhibit a broad asymmetric band in the region 15310 – 16030 cm^{-1} which is assigned to $(d-d)$ transition. They also exhibit another strong band in the region 23800 – 25000 cm^{-1} and this band is due to the ligand to metal charge transfer transition rather than due to dimetallic species.^(48–50)

Tetragonal Cu(II) complexes involve three transitions viz ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}$; ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$ and ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$ but bands due to these transitions usually overlap to give one broad absorption band. Present Cu(II) complexes show one such broad band around 18800 cm^{-1} suggesting that these complexes are of tetragonal type.

Copper(II) complex shows magnetic moment around 1.82 B.M. which is close to the spin only value for a d^9 ion. The electronic spectrum displays a broad band in vicinity of 17980 cm^{-1} which may be assigned to ${}^2E_g \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}$ transition indicating the presence of copper(II) ion in an octahedral field. The magnetic moment of the complex indicates no copper–copper interaction. The absence of any band below 10000 cm^{-1} or above 17000 cm^{-1} rules out the possibility of tetrahedral or square planar symmetry. Broadness of the band in complexes may be due to Jahn Teller distortion.^(51–55)

Since only a single $d-d$ broad band at ca. 10800 cm^{-1} has been observed in the complexes reported herein, it is concluded that all the three transitions lie within this

broad envelope. Thus, these complexes approximate to D_{4h} symmetry. An approximate value of 10Dq may be obtained from the expression:

$$10Dq = v_3 - \frac{1}{2} v_1 - \frac{1}{3} (v_3 - v_2)$$

If it is assumed that the splitting of the states due to the tetragonal field follows the barycentre rule. The calculated 10Dq values are also included in Table 5.9–5.10. However, the effect and magnitude of distortion from normal square plane is not known with certainty.

Table 5.1: Electronic spectral data (cm⁻¹) of VO(IV) complexes of (C₁₇H₂₁N₇S)

S.No.	Complexes	Band-I $d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{xz}, d_{yz}$	Band-II $d_{xy} \rightarrow dx^2-y^2$	Band-III $d_{xy} \rightarrow dz^2$
1.	[VOCl ₂ (C ₁₇ H ₂₁ N ₇ S)]	12970	15360	–
2.	[VOBr ₂ (C ₁₇ H ₂₁ N ₇ S)]	12640	15460	21715
3.	[VOI ₂ (C ₁₇ H ₂₁ N ₇ S)]	12920	15810	21865
4.	[VO(NO ₃) ₂ (C ₁₇ H ₂₁ N ₇ S)]	13000	15510	22120
5.	[VO(NCS) ₂ (C ₁₇ H ₂₁ N ₇ S)]	12980	15770	21880
6.	[VO(ClO ₄) ₂ (C ₁₇ H ₂₁ N ₇ S).H ₂ O]	13010	15220	22290

Table 5.2: Electronic spectral data (cm^{-1}) of VO(IV) complexes of ($\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{33}\text{N}_7\text{S}$)

S.No.	Complexes	Band-I	Band-II	Band-III
		$d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{xz}, d_{yz}$	$d_{xy} \rightarrow dx^2-y^2$	$dxy \rightarrow dz^2$
1.	$[\text{VOCl}_2(\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{33}\text{N}_7\text{S})]$	12940	15402	21710
2.	$[\text{VOBr}_2(\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{33}\text{N}_7\text{S})]$	12810	15180	15190
3.	$[\text{VOI}_2(\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{33}\text{N}_7\text{S})]$	12605	15790	21840
4.	$[\text{VO}(\text{NO}_3)_2(\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{33}\text{N}_7\text{S})]$	13020	15605	22010
5.	$[\text{VO}(\text{NCS})_2(\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{33}\text{N}_7\text{S})]$	12840	15470	22298
6.	$[\text{VO}(\text{ClO}_4)_2(\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{33}\text{N}_7\text{S}) \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]$	12716	15515	22105

Table 5.3: Electronic spectral data (cm^{-1}) of VO(IV) complexes of ($\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{21}\text{N}_7\text{S}$)

S.No.	Complexes	Band-I	Band-II	Band-III
		$d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{xz}, d_{yz}$	$d_{xy} \rightarrow dx^2-y^2$	$dxy \rightarrow dz^2$
1.	$[\text{VOCl}_2(\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{21}\text{N}_7\text{S})]$	13316	17255	24080
2.	$[\text{VOBr}_2(\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{21}\text{N}_7\text{S})]$	13515	17015	25015
3.	$[\text{VOI}_2(\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{21}\text{N}_7\text{S})]$	13213	17117	24806
4.	$[\text{VO}(\text{NO}_3)_2(\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{21}\text{N}_7\text{S})]$	12910	17220	25212
5.	$[\text{VO}(\text{NCS})_2(\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{21}\text{N}_7\text{S})]$	13496	16918	25000
6.	$[\text{VO}(\text{ClO}_4)_2(\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{21}\text{N}_7\text{S}) \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]$	13407	17010	24900

Table 5.4: Electronic spectral bands (cm^{-1}) and ligand field parameters of Cobalt(II) complexes of ($\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_8\text{S}$)

S.No.	Complexes	ν_2 ${}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^4\text{A}_{2g}$	ν_3 ${}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{P})$	Dq (cm^{-1})	B (cm^{-1})	β	Dq/B	ν_1 (cm^{-1})
1.	$[\text{CoCl}_2(\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_8\text{S})\text{H}_2\text{O}]$	15515	20840	862	957	0.854	0.90	7962
2.	$[\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2(\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_8\text{S})\text{H}_2\text{O}]$	15912	20510	856	952	0.850	0.89	7833
3.	$[\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_2(\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_8\text{S})\text{H}_2\text{O}]$	15460	20680	860	954	0.851	0.90	7811
4.	$[\text{Co}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2(\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_8\text{S})\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}]$	15514	20740	863	957	0.854	0.90	7962
5.	$[\text{Co}(\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_8\text{S})_2](\text{ClO}_4)_2$	15402	20516	856	951	0.849	0.90	7831

Table 5.5: Electronic spectral bands (cm^{-1}) and ligand field parameters of Cobalt(II) complexes of ($\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{21}\text{N}_7\text{S}$)

S.No.	Complexes	ν_2 ${}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^4\text{A}_{2g}$	ν_3 ${}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{P})$	Dq (cm^{-1})	B (cm^{-1})	β	Dq/B	ν_1 (cm^{-1})
1.	$[\text{CoCl}_2(\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{21}\text{N}_7\text{S})\text{H}_2\text{O}]$	18530	20017	1118	1075	0.97	1.04	8779
2.	$[\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2(\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{21}\text{N}_7\text{S})\text{H}_2\text{O}]$	18118	20845	1112	1066	0.96	1.04	8704
3.	$[\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_2(\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{21}\text{N}_7\text{S})\text{H}_2\text{O}]$	18020	20856	1106	1065	0.96	1.03	8698
4.	$[\text{Co}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2(\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{21}\text{N}_7\text{S})\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}]$	18190	20040	1107	1065	0.98	1.03	8717
5.	$[\text{Co}(\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{21}\text{N}_7\text{S})_2](\text{ClO}_4)_2$	18530	20025	1121	1066	0.97	1.05	8780

Table 5.6: Electronic spectral bands (cm^{-1}) and ligand field parameters of Cobalt(II) complexes of ($\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_6\text{S}$)

S.No.	Complexes	ν_2 ${}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^4\text{A}_{2g}$	ν_3 ${}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F}) \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{P})$	Dq (cm^{-1})	B (cm^{-1})	β	Dq/B	ν_1 (cm^{-1})
1.	$[\text{CoCl}_2(\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_6\text{S})\text{H}_2\text{O}]$	18160	20040	1113	1075	0.98	1.03	8762
2.	$[\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2(\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_6\text{S})\text{H}_2\text{O}]$	18500	20826	1102	1065	0.96	1.03	8686
3.	$[\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_2(\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_6\text{S})\text{H}_2\text{O}]$	18145	20113	1101	1065	0.96	1.03	8683
4.	$[\text{Co}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2(\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_6\text{S})\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}]$	18110	20840	1105	1070	0.97	1.03	8704
5.	$[\text{Co}(\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_6\text{S})_2](\text{ClO}_4)_2$	18030	20847	1105	1066	0.98	1.03	8704

Table 5.7: Electronic spectral bands (cm^{-1}) and ligand field parameters of Nickel(II) complexes of ($\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_8\text{S}$)

S.No.	Complexes	ν_1	ν_2	ν_3	Dq (cm^{-1})	B (cm^{-1})	B
1.	$[\text{NiCl}_2(\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_8\text{S})\text{H}_2\text{O}]$	8280 10940	17713	27218	1094	794	0.76
2.	$[\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2(\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_8\text{S})\text{H}_2\text{O}]$	8240 10880	17550	27512	1088	830	0.79
3.	$[\text{Ni}(\text{NCS})_2(\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_8\text{S})\text{H}_2\text{O}]$	8230 10825	17547	26967	1082	806	0.77
4.	$[\text{Ni}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2(\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_8\text{S})\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}]$	10970	16960	27416	1097	748	0.73
5.	$[\text{Ni}(\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_8\text{S})_2](\text{ClO}_4)_2$	10920	17725	27020	1092	793	0.76

Table 5.8: Electronic spectral bands (cm^{-1}) and ligand field parameters of Nickel(II) complexes of ($\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{21}\text{N}_7\text{S}$)

S.No.	Complexes	λ_{max} (cm^{-1})			Dq (cm^{-1})	B (cm^{-1})	B
		ν_1	ν_2	ν_3			
1.	$[\text{NiCl}_2(\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{21}\text{N}_7\text{S})\text{H}_2\text{O}]$	9098	15165	25040	909	988	0.91
2.	$[\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2(\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{21}\text{N}_7\text{S})\text{H}_2\text{O}]$	9617	15400	25670	961	1044	0.96
3.	$[\text{Ni}(\text{NCS})_2(\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{21}\text{N}_7\text{S})\text{H}_2\text{O}]$	9813	16720	24520	981	1066	0.98
4.	$[\text{Ni}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2(\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{21}\text{N}_7\text{S})\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}]$	9933	16680	24414	993	1079	0.99
5.	$[\text{Ni}(\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{21}\text{N}_7\text{S})_2](\text{ClO}_4)_2$	9614	16210	24419	961	1044	0.96

Table 5.9: Electronic Spectral bands (cm^{-1}) of Copper(II) complexes of ($\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_8\text{S}$) and ($\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{21}\text{N}_7\text{S}$)

S.No.	Complex	(d-d) band	CT-bands		10Dq
1.	$[\text{CuCl}_2(\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_8\text{S})\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}]$	15830	23090	28776	7910
2.	$[\text{CuBr}_2(\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_8\text{S})\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}]$	16260	23550	28632	8130
3.	$[\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2(\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_8\text{S})\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}]$	16130	22910	28743	8065
4.	$[\text{Cu}(\text{NCS})_2(\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_8\text{S})\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}]$	16215	23216	28707	8107
5.	$[\text{Cu}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2(\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_8\text{S})\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}]$	16316	23003	28810	8158
6.	$[\text{CuCl}_2(\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{21}\text{N}_7\text{S})\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}]$	15817	23132	28776	7908
7.	$[\text{CuBr}_2(\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{21}\text{N}_7\text{S})\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}]$	16070	23090	28712	8035
8.	$[\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2(\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{21}\text{N}_7\text{S})\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}]$	16040	23014	28765	8020
9.	$[\text{Cu}(\text{NCS})_2(\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{21}\text{N}_7\text{S})\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}]$	16160	23013	26905	8080
10.	$[\text{Cu}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2(\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{21}\text{N}_7\text{S})\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}]$	15810	23092	28773	8905

Table 5.10: Electronic Spectral bands (cm^{-1}) of Copper(II) complexes of ($\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_6\text{S}$) and ($\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{21}\text{N}_7\text{S}$)

S.No.	Complex	(d-d) band	CT-bands		10Dq
1.	$[\text{CuCl}_2(\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_6\text{S}) \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]$	16030	23020	26645	8015
2.	$[\text{CuBr}_2(\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_6\text{S}) \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]$	16009	23035	26918	8000
3.	$[\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2(\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_6\text{S}) \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]$	16322	23090	28775	8161
4.	$[\text{Cu}(\text{NCS})_2(\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_6\text{S}) \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]$	16004	23110	28860	8002
5.	$[\text{Cu}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2(\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_6\text{S}) \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]$	16100	22914	28775	8050
6.	$[\text{CuCl}_2(\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{21}\text{N}_7\text{S}) \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]$	16323	23205	28709	8150
7.	$[\text{CuBr}_2(\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{21}\text{N}_7\text{S}) \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]$	16217	22927	28763	8108
8.	$[\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2(\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{21}\text{N}_7\text{S}) \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]$	15840	23020	28818	7920
9.	$[\text{Cu}(\text{NCS})_2(\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{21}\text{N}_7\text{S}) \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]$	16130	23016	26632	8065
10.	$[\text{Cu}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2(\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{21}\text{N}_7\text{S}) \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]$	16218	23133	28713	8109

CHAPTER–V

REFERENCES

1. C.J. Ballhausen, "Introduction to ligand field theory" McGraw Hill, New York (1962).
2. C.K. Jorgensen, "Absorption spectra and chemical bonding in complexes", Pergamon Press, New York (1962).
3. C.K. Jorgensen, "Discussion Faraday Soc." 26 (1958) 110.
4. C.K. Jorgensen, "The Nephelauxetic Series Progress in Inorganic Chemistry" (Ed. F.A. Cotton, Vol. 4 P. 73 Interscience, New York (1962).
5. C.K. Jorgensen, "Orbitals in Atoms and Molecules" Academic Press, London (1962).
6. C.K. Jorgensen, "Modern Aspects of Ligand field theory" North Holland Publishing Co., Amsterdam, 1971.
7. J. Selbin, Chem. Rev. 65 (1965) 153.
8. J. Selbin, Coord. Chem. Rev.; 1 (1966) 293.
9. C. Furlani, Ric. Sci.; 27 (1957) 1141.
10. C.K. Jorgensen, Acta Chem. Scand 11 (1957) 73.
11. C.J. Ballhensen and H.B. Gray, Inorg. Chem; 1 (1962) 111.
12. J. Selbin and T.R. Ortolano, J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem. 26 (1964) 37.
13. J. Selbin, T.R. Ortolano and F.J. Smith, Inorg. Chem; 2 (1963) 1315.
14. G. Basu, K. Xeranos and R.L. Belford, Inorg. Chem. 3 (1964) 929.
15. T.R. Ortolano, J. Selbin and S.P. McGlynn, J. Chem. Phys. 41 (1964) 1115.
16. J. Selbin and L. Morpurgo, J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem. 27 (1965) 673.
17. H.B. Gray and C.R. Hare, Inorg. Chem; 1 (1962) 363.
18. I. Bernal and P.H. Rieger, Inorg. Chem; 2 (1963) 256.
19. S. Yamada and Y. Kuge, Bull. Chem. Soc. Japan 42 (1969) 152.
20. L. Sacconi and V. Compigilli, Inorg. Chem; 5 (1966) 606.
21. Y. Kuge and S. Yamada, Bull. Chem. Soc. Japan, 43 (1970) 3972.

22. L.G. Vonquickenhorne and S.P. McGlynn, *Theor. Chim. Acta* 9 (1968) 390.
23. A.B.P. Lever, *Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy* 2nd Ed. (Elsevier Amsterdam) 1984.
24. R.L. Dutta & A. Syamal, *Elements of Magnetochemistry*, 2nd Ed. (Affl. East West Press Pvt. Ltd., New Delhi), 1993.
25. G. Wilkinson, *Comprehensive Coordination Chemistry*, Vol. 3, Main Group and Early Transition Elements (Pergamon Press, Oxford) 1987.
26. J. Reedijk, W.L. Driessen and W.L. Groeneveld, *Recl. Trav. Chim.* 80 (1969) 1095.
27. Y. Tanabe and S. Sugano, *J. Phys. Soc. (Japan)* 9 (1954) 753, 766.
28. A.B.P. Lever, *J. Chem. Edu.* 45 (1968) 711.
29. F.A. Cotton and J.P. Fackler (Jr.), *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 83 (1961) 2818.
30. R.D. Archer, *Inorg. Chem.* 2 (1963) 292.
31. T. Tarutelli, P. Riccieri & C. Furlani, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.* 31 (1969) 3585.
32. T. Tarutelli, P. Riccieri & C. Furlani, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.* 33 (1971) 1389.
33. T. Tarutelli, P. Riccieri and C. Furlani, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.* 34 (1972) 999.
34. C.R. Hare and C.J. Ballhausen, *J. Chem. Phys.* 40 (1964) 788, 792.
35. J.T. Summery and J.V. Quagliano, *Inorg. Chem.* 3 (1964) 1767.
36. R.W. Kiser and T.W. Lapp, *Inorg. Chem.* 1 (1962) 401.
37. S. Buffagain, L.M. Vallerino and J.V. Quagliano, *Inorg. Chem.* 3 (1964) 486.
38. D.M.L. Goodgame, M. Goodgame & M.J. Weeks, *J. Chem. Soc.* 5194 (1964).
39. A.B.P. Lever, S.M. Nelson & T.M. Shepherd, *Inorg. Chem.* 8 (1965) 810.
40. S. Buffagain, L.M. Vallerino and J.V. Quagliano, *Inorg. Chem.* 7 (1964) 671.
41. A.B.P. Lever, J. Lewis and R.S. Nyholm, *J. Chem. Soc.* (1964) 4761.
42. D.M.L. Goodgame and L.M. Venanzi, *J. Chem. Soc.* (1963) 5909.
43. A.B.P. Lever, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*; 3 (1968) 119.
44. E. König, *The Nephelauxetic effect structure and bonding* Springer, New York (1971).

45. F.A. Cotton and G. Wilkinson, *Advanced Inorganic Chemistry* (Wiley Inter Science, New York) 1988.
46. S.Chowdhury, M.G.B.Drew & D.Datta, *New J. Chem.* 27 (2003) 831.
47. M.G.B. Drew, D. Parvi, S. De, J.P. Naskar & D. Datta, *Eur. J. Inorg. Chem.* (2006) 4026.
48. M.G.B. Drew, D. Parvi, S.De, S. Chowdhury, & D.Datta, *New J. Chem.* 31 (2007) 1763.
49. S.De, M.G.B. Drew, H.S. Rzepa, & Datta, *New J. Chem.* 32 (2008) 1831.
50. M.B.Halli, P.Vithal Reddy, K.Shiva Kumar, A.Basavaraja, B.A.Jumnal & B.Patil Vijaya Laxmi, *J. Ind. Council Chem.* 27 (2010) 58.
51. S.El Tabl Abdou & M. Issa Raafat, *J. Coord. Chem.* 57 (2004) 509.
52. M.B. Halli & V.B. Patil, *Ind. J. Chem.* 50A (2011) 664.
53. Geetika Borah & D. Boruah, *Ind. Jour. of Chem.* 51A (2012) 444.
54. V.P. Singh, P. Gupta, & N. Lal, *Russian J. Coord. Chem.* 34 (2008) 270.
55. R.R.Pulimamidi, Raju Nomula & V.R.Karnati, *Ind. J. Chem.* 48A (2009) 1638.